

Humidity responsivity of CYTOP-XYLEX fibre Bragg grating sensors

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ABSTRACT

CYTOP-XYLEX fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors' response to relative humidity (RH) changes is investigated in this work. The intensive research on CYTOP polymer optical fibre sensors relies on their lower optical attenuation compared with the standard poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) based polymer optical fibre sensors. However, CYTOP is a hydrophobic polymer and cannot be used as a standalone material in humidity-sensing applications. A hydrophilic material is required to be used as fibre over-cladding for RH detection; the water swelling occurring in the over-cladding material can strain the FBG structure located in the CYTOP core. In this work, a novel CYTOP fibre with a XYLEX over-cladding material is used to investigate the humidity responsivity of FBG sensors. A femtosecond laser system and the plane-by-plane inscription method were utilised to fabricate the FBG sensors through the fibre over-cladding. The FBG sensors were placed in a climatic chamber with controlled temperature and RH, and their response to RH changes was monitored. The RH sensitivity was evaluated for different temperatures. The results show that the RH sensitivity increases with temperature, whereas the reported RH sensitivity of PMMA-based sensors decreases with temperature. We also report that by applying a pre-strain on the fibre, the RH sensitivity can be eliminated for cross-sensitivity compensation purposes.

Keywords: Polymer optical fibre, fibre Bragg grating sensors, CYTOP, XYLEX, humidity sensitivity

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer optical fibre Bragg grating (POFBG) sensors demonstrate enhanced sensitivity in certain applications compared to the silica fibre Bragg grating sensors^{1,2}. The distinct properties of polymers, such as lower Young's modulus, higher flexibility in bending and higher fracture toughness, render the POFBG sensors a promising alternative for structural health monitoring applications that require detecting displacement, deformation, stress, force and pressure³. The larger and negative thermo-optic coefficient of polymers also offers enhanced sensitivity to temperature changes⁴. POFBG sensors made by hydrophilic polymers can also measure humidity levels and concentrations of water-soluble analytes (e.g., sugar solutions)⁵. The Bragg wavelength shift ($\Delta\lambda_B$) of POFBG due to changes in humidity (ΔH), temperature (ΔT) and strain ($\Delta\varepsilon$) can be expressed as:

$$\Delta\lambda_B = \lambda_B [\Delta H (\eta + \beta) + \Delta T (\zeta + \alpha) + \Delta\varepsilon (1 - \rho)], \quad (1)$$

where λ_B is the initial spectral position of Bragg grating, η is the normalised refractive index change due to humidity change, β is the swelling coefficient, ζ is the thermo-optic coefficient, α is the thermal expansion coefficient, and ρ is the effective photoelastic coefficient. Since the POFBG sensors can detect many parameters simultaneously, compensation techniques (e.g. additional sensors with different responses) are required to extract the actual sensing parameter. The compensation is often challenging when using POFBG sensors because the sensitivity of the sensor can change under different environmental conditions^{4,6}. The complex nature of polymeric materials is often neglected, leading to inconsistent results, especially during temperature and humidity monitoring. The sensitivity of POFBG can change when the fibre is strained, swollen or heated. Therefore, it is essential to characterise the POFBG sensor under different environmental conditions before being used in applications.

This paper investigates the relative humidity (RH) responsivity of a novel POFBG sensor made by CYTOP⁷ core and XYLEX⁸ overcladding. CYTOP is a high-transparent amorphous perfluoropolymer developed to tackle the high optical attenuation exhibited by the standard poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) based polymer optical fibres⁹. However, CYTOP is a hydrophobic polymer (less than 0.01% water absorptivity⁷) and cannot be used as a standalone material in humidity-sensing applications. On the other hand, the XYLEX (a blend of polycarbonate and polyester) has a water

absorptivity of 0.50%⁸. The water swelling occurring in the overcladding material physically expands the fibre and strains the POFBG structure located in the CYTOP core. Since the CYTOP does not absorb water, there is no refractive index change due to humidity change. Only the swelling coefficient of XYLEX affects the POFBG structure. Therefore, as we demonstrate in this work, by applying a fibre pre-strain, the expansion due to swelling can be restricted, resulting in the elimination of RH sensitivity – a method useful for compensation purposes. We also report that the RH sensitivity increases with temperature, whereas the reported RH sensitivity of PMMA-based sensors decreases with temperature¹⁰.

2. FABRICATION OF SENSORS

The POFBG sensors were fabricated in a custom-made fibre (GigaPOF Custom Fibre 250/20, Chromis Fiberoptics) with a CYTOP⁷ graded-index core of 20 ± 4 μm in diameter and a XYLEX⁸ overcladding of 250 ± 5 μm in diameter using a femtosecond laser system (High Q laser femtoREGEN) with 517 nm operating wavelength, 220 fs pulse duration, 2 kHz repetition rate and 20 nJ pulse energy. A plane-by-plane method¹¹ was used for the fabrication of POFBG sensors, in which the Bragg planes are inscribed transversely across the fibre length and centred in the core; the fibre is placed on a high-precision air-bearing translation stage (Aerotech), and the laser beam is focused into the CYTOP fibre core and through XYLEX overcladding by using a long working distance objective lens (50x magnification and 0.42 NA, Mitutoyo). Each POFBG structure has 850 Bragg planes with width of 5 μm . By having smaller Bragg planes than the fibre core size, the number of modes coupling in the Bragg grating structure is reduced, resulting in single-peak reflection. Single Bragg wavelength peak is already demonstrated in the graded-index multimode fibres using the plane-by-plane method¹¹. We note that before the fabrication of POFBG sensors, the fibre was annealed at 70 °C temperature and 40% humidity for more than 2 hours in a climatic chamber. The reason for performing the annealing is to avoid any fibre shrinkage due to temperature exposure, as observed in other temperature characterisation experiments¹². After the fabrication of POFBG sensors, each fibre was connectorised with a standard silica optical fibre for interrogation purposes. The connectorisation was performed by using the butt-coupled technique with a UV adhesive.

3. TEMPERATURE EFFECT ON HUMIDITY RESPONSIVITY

A single POFBG sensor was used to investigate its RH response under different temperature levels. The POFBG was placed in a climatic chamber (Mettler HCP 108) that controls temperature and RH. The spectral position of the sensor was monitored in reflection using the commercial interrogation system (Micron Optics HYPERION si155). To assess the temperature effect on RH sensitivity, the temperature was initially kept constant at 30 ± 1 °C, and the RH was increased in steps of 10% from 40% to 70% and then decreased back to 40%. Then, the temperature was increased by 5 ± 1 °C while keeping the RH at 40%. After the stabilisation of climatic conditions, the same RH cycle steps were repeated. The whole process was repeated for temperatures from 30 ± 1 °C to 45 ± 1 °C, as shown in Figure 1. The total Bragg wavelength shift of the POFBG sensor to RH changes under different temperatures is shown in Figure 2. The RH sensitivities under different temperatures are listed in Table 1. Results show that the RH sensitivity increases with temperature, whereas the reported RH sensitivity of PMMA FBG sensors decreases with temperature¹⁰.

Figure 1: Response of POFBG sensor to RH changes over time under different temperatures.

Figure 2: Bragg wavelength shift of POFBG sensor to RH changes under different temperatures.

Table 1: RH sensitivity of sensor under different temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	RH sensitivity (pm/%RH)
30±1	9.4±0.3
35±1	11.0±0.3
40±1	11.6±0.3
45±1	12.7±0.2

4. PRE-STRAIN EFFECT ON HUMIDITY RESPONSIVITY

An array of 4 POFBG sensors along the same fibre was fabricated to investigate the pre-strain effects on RH sensitivity. First, each POFBG was placed on a linear translation stage and strained to a different value, as listed in Table 2. While the POFBG was strained, a 75-mm glass slide (SuperFrost Ultra Plus, Thermo Scientific) was placed below the POFBG, and a UV adhesive of 5±2 mm in diameter (Norland Optical Adhesive 61) was placed at the edge of the glass slide to fix the fibre. Then, the POFBG sensors were placed in a climatic chamber (Mettler HCP 108) to investigate their RH sensitivity. The climatic chamber controls both temperature and RH, and the actual measurements of temperature and RH were captured by the internal sensors of the climatic chamber. The Bragg wavelength position of sensors was monitored in reflection using a commercial interrogation system (Micron Optics HYPERION si155). To assess the RH sensitivity of each sensor, the temperature was kept constant at 40±1 °C, and the RH was changed in steps. Figure 3 depicts the response of sensors over time when the RH changes in steps of 10% from 30% to 60% and back to 30%. The response of sensors is linear to increasing (Figure 4a) and decreasing (Figure 4b) RH. The results demonstrate that the sensor without any applied pre-strain (POFBG 4) exhibits the highest RH sensitivity. The RH sensitivity can be reduced when a fibre pre-strain is applied because the swelling of XYLEX overcladding is restricted. We demonstrate that the sensor POFBG 1 with 0.50% pre-strain exhibits RH insensitivity – an indication of total restriction of the fibre swelling. The silica (SMF28) FBG sensor, placed in the climatic chamber for comparison purposes, responds to RH changes due to the acrylate coating, which can absorb moisture and expand the grating structure located into the silica core. Table 3 lists the RH sensitivities of sensors, as calculated with linear fitting.

Table 2: Amount of applied pre-strain on POFBG sensors.

Sensor	Pre-strain (%)
POFBG 1	0.50
POFBG 2	0.10
POFBG 3	0.04
POFBG 4	0.00

Figure 3: Response of pre-strain sensors to RH changes over time.

Figure 4: Bragg wavelength shift of POFBG and silica sensors under different pre-strain values with (a) increasing humidity and (b) decreasing humidity.

Table 3: RH sensitivity of sensors under different pre-strain values.

Sensor	Increasing RH (pm/%RH)	Decreasing RH (pm/%RH)
POFBG 1 (0.50% pre-strain)	0.7±0.2	0.3±0.2
POFBG 2 (0.10% pre-strain)	3.9±0.3	3.3±0.2
POFBG 3 (0.04% pre-strain)	9.0±0.5	10.0±0.3
POFBG 4 (0.00% pre-strain)	11.7±0.2	11.0±0.3
Silica FBG (0.00% pre-strain)	1.3±0.2	1.3±0.2

5. CONCLUSION

The RH responsivity of novel CYTOP-XYLEX fibre Bragg grating sensors is investigated in this work. The sensors were placed in a climatic chamber with controlled temperature and RH, and their response to RH changes was monitored. The RH sensitivity was assessed for different temperatures. The results show that the RH sensitivity increases with temperature, whereas the reported RH sensitivity of PMMA-based sensors decreases with temperature. We also report that applying a pre-strain on the fibre can reduce or eliminate the RH sensitivity for cross-sensitivity compensation purposes.

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